

Attraction Considerations

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Abstract

Desires, preferences and the potential for fixations are key influences upon the effectiveness of personal perceptions in the processing of information, which may affect the quality of our decisions and interactions. This paper employs the analogy of sexual attraction as a vehicle to understanding attraction towards concepts. This approach provides the opportunity to consider what are for some, taboo issues within the creative processes. Underpinning this approach is the need to recognise individuality of constructs and categorisations of subjects, objects and events, applied to the development or change of meaning and belief.

‘Desire’ is defined in this paper as the intent to resolve or acquire an objective, which has some pleasurable reward associated with it. In addition, a ‘concept’ is defined as the more tangible development of a seed idea, where perceptions and judgements lead to either physical commitment, or to abandonment. The aim of this paper is to engage its audience in a number of Attraction Considerations (AC’s) relating to desirability, in the context of the judgement of concept attractiveness. It is intended that this analogical approach should encourage examination of the ‘black art’ perception of the creative process. It is proposed that experience of a common wish to suppress externalisation of implicit creative processes, may be the result of an often unvoiced, personal taboo. However, it is further proposed that the value of such considerations would be manifest in the development of personal awareness, thinking skills, and more effective and responsible decision-making.

Keywords: Attraction Considerations, Creative Process, Desire, Concept, Analogy, Taboo, Responsible Decision-Making.

Introduction

When we consider the attraction as an experience, most will think in terms of visual attractiveness initially, but then realise that much of what we might describe in terms of attractive character is based on feelings. Our decisions on attractiveness are actually influenced by all senses providing information. In addition to the sensory channels by which we may receive attraction cues, there are many individual differences in the way that we may interpret those cues, including background experience and personality.

This paper discusses considerations of attractiveness in terms of concept evaluation criteria, which are often an implicit part of the design process. The visualisation and associations, relating to ideas, form emotional relations in our minds, prejudging the desirability of possible outcomes. These may be further rationalised by the natural development of scenarios, forecasting opportunities or threats. It is proposed that the resolution and response options considered would relate to how the individual prioritises their criteria of intent towards each concept. Although emotionally driven responses may include positive actions

like gathering and generating, they may also involve neutral or negative actions like procrastination or disposal. Individual influences may be social and cultural, but also may be due to aesthetic and cognitive preferences in the development of either metaphorical abstractions or concrete definitions. In addition to content and context, time frame can play an important part in the development of constructs, and the individuals' perception of value. Decisions relating to the resolution or sating of desires may be made in a split second, or may take many years from first thought, waiting for sufficient information, opportunity and confidence to be gathered. However, in terms of concept development we need to determine means by which we can make more effective responses to user-centred design intent.

In terms of this paper, the loose definition of a concept will include: the idea of a new product or service, the perceived opportunity of ownership, or the potential boost to self-esteem assumed through action or possession.

Sexual attraction is proposed by the researcher to make an effective vehicle for the comparative analysis of attraction to concept, serving the need to consider the nature and affect of creativity taboos. Other, less complex analogies may not facilitate the same depth of consideration, which is essential to the value of investigations of effective and responsible decision-making. What follows are a number of context headings which have been used to develop the attraction analogy and aid the consideration of attractions' influence upon our conceptual decision-making.

Context

Social Construct and Social Learning Theory

Culture is created through the sharing of commonly held beliefs, confirming for individuals an accepted 'truth'. Responses, which bear out these beliefs, through reward or punishment, serve to reinforce these social constructs, and further serve to maintain stability of social perceptions, by which decisions may be made more efficiently. As part of this process stereotypes and taboos may develop and be used, consciously or sub-consciously, to simplify what might otherwise be a complex process, (Hinton, 2000, and Douglas, 2002). It is on this understanding that it is argued that 'efficient' decision-making does not equate with 'effective' decision-making, which carries a greater sense of value and provides a preferable route to responsibility.

Introversion and Extroversion

A key differentiator between Introverted and Extroverted personalities concerns the level of stimulation required by individuals to balance arousal and attentiveness. (Schmitt and Simonson, 1997). An Introvert might be overwhelmed by the same stimulus that would bore an Extrovert. Extroverts may appear to be very confident, higher risk takers, and yet their personal perception may be that they are well balanced, whilst perceiving the Introverts as timid or overly cautious. Individual balance points for stimulus level do not equate. See figure 1.

Figure 1, Extroversion/Introversion need for stimulation.

Similarly, Introverts may require less feedback to make a response than an Extrovert might, whether of a pessimistic or optimistic nature. Indications of Introvert and Extrovert tendencies may be seen in choice of clothing with plain versus flamboyant, or heard in conversation with closed and quiet versus open and loud. This contributes to our differing perceptions of other peoples' 'taste' and 'needs'. It may also contribute towards which elements of a concept provide sufficient arousal, and either motivation for further development, or if the nature of the arousal is anxiety then the motive for rejection.

Proximity and Involvement Preference

The distance from the source of our desire, and the level of interaction or ownership sought, will be a source of influence upon decisions made. See figure 2. An individual may enjoy the viewing of an attractive actor or actress on a chat show, whilst a face-to-face meeting with that person may in comparison be found to be less enjoyable than the somewhat disconnected situation of viewing. Similarly, the role of supervisor on the development of an interesting concept may lose the level of enjoyment experienced if they deepen their involvement with the detailed design work.

Figure 2, Proximity of involvement with a design project.

Conversely, there are those who may need, or crave, deeper involvement as part of their desire for greater understanding or improved connection, possibly to test the truth of an internal model, and so forecast and judge appropriateness of actions.

The Journey, the Destination and Intimacy

In the acknowledgement of a desire, we may consider the pleasurable reward involved. This might be in terms of the pleasure as a product of the experience of doing, or of completion. For instance, the education process may be viewed as an investment of effort by many, but that the sense of pleasure or relief is experienced on successful completion of the programme of work. However, it is proposed that the idea of rapid education, as envisioned in the film

Matrix, though a means to an end involving a tight timeframe, this would not provide the same sense of value we place on achievement at the conclusion of a conventional educational journey. For many people, but not all it should be said, getting an acceptance when asking a person out on a date for the first time will not result in the same sense of achievement as an acceptance after some rejections from that person. Some designers may be attracted to the challenges of a project with a real risk of failure, whilst others want an easier bet with a possible claim to fame upon successful completion. This difference in perception of task value, relating to ‘the journey’, is one of intimacy.

Figure 3, ‘The Love Triangle’, Sternberg 1998

Intimacy has been described by Sternberg (1998), as one apex of the ‘triangle of love’, with the other two apexes being Passion and Commitment. See figure 3. It is proposed that strong bonding should occur where relationship triangles match proportionally, and that there may be layers to these triangles, for instance between the ideal and the real. The proportion of these triangles may change as a result of experience along the journey. So the relationship to a subject, object or event may be viewed at any point as constructive or destructive.

In terms of a concept it is proposed that the required and available attraction cues could involve the use of a larger number of apexes dealing with key issues, whereas for a product that is mapped over time such referencing would reflect market changes.

Interpretation and Interpolation of Attraction Cues

The following exercise may help to provide the context for discussion within this sub-section. Take a DVD or movie-file of an attractive film star or singer, select a two or three second section of facial motion and view it a couple of times to absorb what is believed to be occurring visually and emotionally. Now view it again but this time frame by frame, notice how in the detail of slow motion there appear to be a number of other facial expressions that were not initially apparent. We fill in the gaps, in a gestalt sense, interpolating between one expression and another, guided by expectations or in a fashion that supports our preferred belief.

Interpretation of expression is influenced by the situation surrounding the event, and personal or social judgement of appropriateness or potential conflict, regardless of potential validity of the other fleeting 'micro-expressions'. Though micro-expressions are a product of interpolation between intended expressions, some may reveal an otherwise masked mood or attitude. Consciously we acknowledge these primary expressions in our interpersonal communications if we look for them, or they conflict with our expectations. However, the meaning embedded in the secondary, 'micro-expressions', often remains implicit, or subliminal, with possible affect upon us emotionally. On reflection they may be acknowledged as 'just a feeling'.

Similarly, products like clothes and cars provide aesthetic cues to desirability. Devoid of such cues they would not reach the marketplace. The emotive drama of primary expressions can be used to sell and reinforce expectations of popularity. Products are designed and manufactured with the intent to provide the levels of desirability appropriate to their marketplace. However, if we take a long look over a concept model bath for example, there will be found angles of view and details, which do not appeal to the same degree as the primary attractors. However, the issues of compromise may be outweighed consciously by our concern over key features.

Figure 4, Views of a concept bath.

In terms of sketch concept evaluation and selection we are afforded little or no physical ‘look before you commit’ opportunity. Commitment has first to be made to a physical or virtual prototype, see figure 4, in order to compare the reality against the intent, as a forecast of the potential contained or still to be realised.

Fantasy versus Reality

In order to set the context for this sub-section another exercise is suggested. Still images of an attractive film star or singer may be used to consider perceptual conflict, which in this example involves clothing and contact. In the first instance, visually, these characters’ clothing may initiate a positive emotional response, which may encourage an individual to desire contact with their chosen character. However, contact in reality might be found to produce conflict between the senses of sight and touch. For example armour provides a sense of strength of character, and yet is unyielding to intimate contact.

It is key that Fantasy, and its accompanying ambiguity, is appreciated as a creative aid for open-minded approaches to opportunity, providing a divergent perspective. However, the assessment of detail against criteria as a process, confirms the Reality in a convergent perspective, the very means by which we develop concepts into designs and then products. This process of consideration is about balance and appropriateness to position within the development process, and appreciating the value of both Fantasy and Reality. This is not to suggest that the design process should run from complete Fantasy to total Reality. Without an element of Reality, risk may be considered too high to invest in developmental engagement.

Without an element of Fantasy a product or service may prove to lack marketability. In addition, if the Fantasy element is discordant the user experience will conflict with expectations and discourage continuation.

Humour and Offence

It has been proposed, (Hilton, 2001), that humour could be categorised and presented in a family tree format to better understand the dynamic contribution of humour to the creative processes and decision-making. See figure 5. Conflict or incongruity within a relationship or a situation can be perceived as humorous and potentially attractive, even though this may be manifest as either inclusive or exclusive in nature.

The attraction of humour is a socialising drive, which itself establishes the foundations for more abstract scenarios including further humour, which encourage greater creative expression.

Humour may entertain through reference to taboo subjects, which suggests that for both social and design benefits we need to steer close to, and constantly reassess, the perceived boundaries, which is a form of risk-homeostasis. Taboos are created and then learned socially through context, and are then reinforced through our skirting or avoidance behaviour. In short, it is argued that we personally and socially create our own sources of offence, whilst ironically perceiving the offences to be wholly initiated by external parties.

Figure 5, A family tree of Humour, Hilton 2001

This leads us to reconsider the Introversion/Extroversion issues of need for arousal in terms of balance between attraction and disgust, as a potential dynamic for passion and need for resolution, within our relationships and creative processes.

Chemistry and Seduction

Beyond visual attractiveness and social/intellectual compatibility there is a degree of 'chemistry' involved in the dynamics of attraction, which may be a source of great pleasure or conflict and confusion. A relationship may breakdown though partners consider each other visually and intellectually attractive, just because the 'X' factor is missing. Conversely, two individuals may not be attracted to one another visually or intellectually and yet sense a dynamic connection through the 'X' factor.

In terms of consumerism, our decision to purchase a product may be down to a need for 75%+ consistency with our needs, yet it may only take 2% of the 'X' factor to seduce the consumer into a purchase that may not actually be adequate for the intended purpose. The 'love is blind' scenario.

Once a decision has been made and the initial discrepancies with intent identified, a period of rationalisation generally takes place by which the individual seeks to justify to themselves and others the reason for their decision, cognitive dissonance, as if to deny the element of seduction or a possible poor decision. There is no reason to believe that this process is confined to relationships and purchases. Once a level of commitment to concept is reached it may prove more of a challenge to remain open-minded. Seduced by the flow and the increasing sense of ownership, but possibly that sparkle of promise too, which is no guarantee that the rest of the design will prove workable.

We might also consider seduction as the conscious or unconscious act of employing attraction cues to coerce and manipulate others decisions and responses. In these terms seduction may also be used to distract. There is an obvious ethical issue for consideration here, as the designer may be employed to seduce the customer into buying the clients' product or service without due consideration of their needs. The responsible approach would be to develop attraction cues which will honour compatibility with user needs.

Obsession

Wishes can become obsessive if the act or the vision of feeding them is in some way reinforced physically, emotionally or socially, especially noticeable in children and young adults. These desires may strengthen individual perceptions to a sense of real need, in seeking to dress like the stars beyond appropriate norms, ride a motorbike at speed, or decline interaction with others in order to successfully compete against computer games. Cushman (1990) suggests that a failure of community spirit since World War Two has created a condition he called the *empty self*, where individuals seek to fill the hole in their soul, sucked into consumerism and drawn into religious or mystical followings.

Obsession and obsessive behaviour goes beyond keen interest. This overpowering sense of need causes individuals to become irrational, or less rational, as their body attempts to prepare for action with a view to obtaining the object of their desire. At times these fixations can influence ability to focus upon other needs. However, since obsessions are linked to individual personality traits and experiences, the designer would have to work at the level of social systems, media and services to reduce reinforcement of obsessive behaviour.

Boundary Transgression and Change

In terms of this sub-section, reference to boundaries includes both personally and socially constructed limitations, such as status and taboo issues. Transgression then, includes the investigation or crossing of these boundaries. Though transgression is more often framed in the negative sense, it may be viewed in the positive as innovative behaviour. Indeed, the negative perceptions of transgression could be argued to be conservative or even discriminatory if previous justification fails to sound rational under social, economic or technological change.

The generation and selection of concepts requires a sense of direction and balance of transgression in a context of consumer diversity. The designer is required to appreciate the conflicts involved and social constraints upon the user. This is particularly notable in the fashion industries where there are markets for a range of gender needs. Society is moving towards an understanding that a polarized view of masculine and feminine is rather naïve.

In terms of design, the transgression approach considers more than gender and sexuality as it looks to question other cultural and lifestyle 'norms'. It might be argued that if we are to

resolve some of our product contributions to ecological damage, the answer may lay in the direction of replacing tangible products with intangible services, or higher investment long-life community resources, a definite transgression from the anticipated personal possession.

Timing is important to successful transgressions, where the need for change is forecast and reflected upon, as seen in trend cycles but also in progress. Technology and communication in our developing global community now enable us to accept new concepts faster than ever before, accelerating the rate of change. Transgressions into fringe areas develop new attractions, as fears and prejudices are proven false, and early adopters promote the value of the next innovation.

Attraction Considerations

Taking a Cognitive Behaviour Therapy approach to questioning our perceptions and necessitating the citing of evidence to support beliefs, we may now ask the following questions to assess our personal choice of a concept development:

1. What proof is there that the target market will share your attraction?
2. Is there any evidence to suggest you have a more Introverted or Extroverted sense of attraction than the market norm?
3. Is your attraction related to level of involvement?
4. Is your attraction related to the concept's phase of development?
5. How many attraction cues can you define for the concept?
6. How many of the attraction cues are fantasy ('what if' - concept) related?
7. How many of the attraction cues are reality ('we can' - product) related?
8. Does avoidance of offence play a key part in the attraction?
9. Does an 'X' factor exist that others would be attracted to?
10. Are you overly focused in your valuing and definition of key cues?
11. Are the attraction cues gender biased?
12. Does the attraction involve appropriate transgressions or breakthroughs?
13. Are the attraction cues balanced across the range of requirements?
14. Are the attraction cues returning to mind during other activities?
15. Is the attraction experienced anticipated to be sustainable by others?

Methodology

The approach for this programme of research was to use the list of Attraction Considerations (AC's) at the concept review point of an industrial design student project. The presentation of the list followed the delivery of a seminar about attractions' potential to influence decision-making, which was based upon the context content described above. The students were initially requested to note down their favoured three concepts, with comments, then following the seminar they were asked to record their immediate responses to the fifteen AC prompts, in terms of their noted project concepts.

The hypothesis was that this approach would enable reflection upon attraction issues to aid the identification and avoidance of personal and social fixations, and provide the opportunity to reassess developmental criteria towards a more user-centre design.

Results

The seminar was received well by the student group. However, as anticipated they found it difficult to talk openly about the subject, either in terms of the sexual relationship analogy, or the deeper question relating to their own creative processes.

The written responses varied widely, with few students responding to all questions. Though some students communicated uncertainty about their thinking and concluded that they should have considered the end user more, some students appeared to have gained confidence as a result of justifying their decisions.

Discussion

Issues relating to sex, such as relationships, attraction and sexuality are very difficult to research effectively, especially where participants perceive it difficult to distance themselves from their responses. This is in part due to the taboo nature and unacceptability of certain subjects being voiced, though ironically there is a greater interest in listening to volunteered information. It has similarly been noted, Hilton (2000), that some designers decline invitations to talk about personal creative processes, though they may be keen to hear of others'. Beyond individuals feeling laid open to criticism, it was noted by some that there was almost a fear of losing the 'black art' once deep contemplation had taken place.

Although attraction is one of a number of factors influencing decision-making, without raising awareness of such factors we are more reliant upon intuition to guide our decision-making process. Making emotionally based responses, initiated by a 'feeling of knowing'. (Koriat, 1993). It is proposed that some of the AC's may prove a positive future source of influence for individuals, but as has been found through previous research, (Hilton 2002), the value of the AC's is not likely to be maximised without repeated practice, to develop skill.

Conclusion

The intention to provide a checklist of Attraction Considerations with a focus upon conceptual development and responsible decision-making was realised by using a sexual attraction analogy to develop a breadth of AC's. However, the taboo nature of the topic that threatened to restrict free discussion, even in terms of conceptual attraction, certainly proved to be so in the outcome. Though the presentation was reported to be stimulating, without an extended period of active immersion with the AC's the participants were clearly unwilling to comment upon potential personal changes to the subjective influences within their decision-making processes.

Although this programme of research was not able to engage the participant in more open and deeper discussion the use of the analogy and the development of the AC's is considered to have opened opportunities for further work in this area.

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